

A Review on Positive Emotions and their Role in Mental Health

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Positive emotions play an important role in mental health and well-being. This study examined the effects of emotions including optimism, love, hope, and gratitude, joy, etc. Positive emotions help to improve relationships with others, lower stress and anxiety, and boost resilience. These feelings also have beneficial impacts on physical health, including boosting immunity and reducing stress hormones. Positive emotions are important for mental health because they encourage people to get over obstacles and develop resilience. This study's overall findings indicate how important it is to cultivate and nourish positive emotions in order to support mental wellness. This review is important because it highlights the less explored but impactful role of positive emotions in enhancing immune function, improving stress and overall health.

Keywords: Positive emotion, mental health, joy, gratitude, optimism

The way to overcome negative thoughts and destructive emotions is to develop opposing, positive emotions that are stronger and more powerful

Dalai Lama

Positive emotions are pleasurable and desired emotional reactions that can be expressed by favorable incidents, experiences, or thoughts (Fredrickson, 2001). Experiences of pleasure, satisfaction, and enjoyment that contribute to subjective well-being indicate positive emotions (Diener & Diener, 1996). Joy, gratitude, love, hope, pride, optimism, serenity, amusement, inspiration, and interest are some of positive emotions (Fredrickson, 2001). The four positive emotions, joy, interest, contentment, and love, can be used to describe emotional states according to the broaden-and-build model. This theory claims that cultivating positive emotions not only promotes immediate well-being but also promotes psychological development and flourishing (Fredrickson, 2001). According to Fredrickson (2001), joy is an affective state characterized by sentiments of satisfaction and pleasure that enhance social interaction and increase a person's cognitive skills. On the other hand, gratitude is a prosocially emotion that involves acknowledging and valuing the advantages or kindness received from others, hence enhancing interpersonal connections and elevating life happiness (Emmons & McCullough, 2004). It has been demonstrated that optimism enhances coping mechanisms, resilience, and general mental health. It is a generalized expectation of favorable future outcomes (Carver et al., 2010). Hope has been associated with

improved psychological adjustment and goal attainment (Snyder et al., 2000) while gratitude has been found to build social interactions, which act as protective factors for psychological well-being (Algoe, 2012). These results are corroborated by meta-analyses, which demonstrate the efficacy of positive psychology therapies, such as kindness, gratitude, and optimism training, in enhancing well-being and lowering depressive symptoms in a number of demographics (Bolier et al., 2013; Hendriks et al., 2020). Thus, knowing how positive emotions work is essential to creating treatments that enhance mental health and overall quality.

Mental health is defined as a condition of emotional, psychological, and social well-being that affects an individual's thoughts and behaviors, allowing them to overcome life's obstacles, reach their full possibilities, work efficiently, and give back to their communities (World Health Organization, 2001). People who are in good mental health have the capacity to control stress, develop resilience, maintain positive relationships, and make valuable contributions to society (World Health Organization, 2004). Poor psychological states like stress, worry, and depression frequently raise the risk of chronic illnesses like diabetes and cardiovascular disease; therefore, it is directly related to physical health (World Health Organization, 2018).

Mental health is not just the absence of mental illnesses, it also includes feeling happy, content, and having purpose in life (World Health Organization, 2004). Thereby, keeping and improving mental health is very important for the growth of healthy societies as well as for the happiness and productivity of individuals. "A state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively, and can contribute to his or her community" that's how the World Health Organization (WHO, 2001) defines mental health. Mental health is becoming equally necessary as physical health, and it is impossible to overlook due to divergent opinions on health. Poor mental state of mind is now a major public health concern worldwide. The World Health Organisation (WHO) reported in 2022 that 970 million individuals worldwide experienced mental health issues in 2019 (WHO, 2022).

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Positive Emotion and Mental Health

Positive emotions such as happiness, gratitude and optimism have been discovered to be extremely important in physical and mental well-being. However, much of the existing literature focuses more on negative emotions and their impact on health. Compared to their less anxious peers, whites and blacks with high anxiety had two to three times higher levels of hypertension (Jonas et al., 1997). When we experience positive emotion, it helps us to think in a creative and thoughtful way (Fredrickson, 2001). Due to being able to identify a variety of different ways to cope in the face of adversity, people who experience higher frequencies of positive emotions have a better ability to manage stress and cultivate higher degrees of resilience (Cohn et al., 2009; Fredrickson, 2009; Gloria et al., 2013). Positive emotions may help people recover from depression and promote mental health flourishing based on a range of evidence in the field of emotions (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005; Richman et al., 2005; Fredrickson & Cohn, 2008). Positive emotions are helpful for improving mental health because they increase psychological resilience, lower stress levels, and promote general well-being (Fredrickson, 2001). Positive emotions may help to protect against anxiety and depression by promoting adaptive coping and enhancing social support systems (Tugade & Fredrickson, 2004). Additionally, positive emotions like optimism and gratitude have been linked to more effective relationships with other people, increased life satisfaction, and better stress management (Emmons & McCullough, 2004; Carver et al., 2010). In this sense, positive emotions strongly promote long-term psychological development and mental health maintenance rather than short-term pleasure. By increasing resilience, encouraging adaptive coping, and decreasing psychological distress, positive emotions significantly contribute to the mental health improvement of COVID-19 patients (Yıldırım & Arslan, 2020).

Positive feelings including gratitude, hope, and optimism have been found to protect against anxiety and depression symptoms throughout the pandemic, assisting patients in adjusting to uncertainty and sickness (Tugade & Fredrickson, 2004). The effects are further supported by evidence from intervention studies: digital multicomponent positive psychology programs delivered during the pandemic improved well-being and reduced stress among adults with mild to moderate distress (Tönis et al., 2024) while gratitude-based activities significantly improved positive affect and reduced depressive symptoms across populations (Diniz et al., 2023). Online kindness and appreciation exercises were linked to increased life satisfaction, fewer negative emotions, and decreased COVID-19 anxiety in student populations (Datu & Mateo, 2021). Promoting positive emotions through techniques like mindfulness and gratitude journaling can improve emotional control and help in recovery, according to research done on individuals with depression and chronic illnesses (Sin & Lyubomirsky, 2009). When taken as a whole, these results highlight the significance of positive emotions as critical components of mental health and long-term psychological resilience.

Joy

As a fundamentally positive feeling, joy is crucial for fostering psychological well-being and enhancing mental health. Other comparably high arousal feelings like joy and happiness (sometimes called excitement or laughter; Ruch, 1993) share

conceptual space with joy (de Riveria et al., 1989). Joy can be used equally with happiness (Lazarus, 1991). Joyful times can reduce the impact of unpleasant emotions by lowering stress responses and promoting a faster emotional recovery (Fredrickson & Joiner, 2002). By encouraging playfulness and connecting, joy also improves social interactions and builds supportive relationships, which are a significant defence against mental illness (Shiota et al., 2014). Additionally, it has been shown that fostering joy by practices like humor, enjoyment, or significant encounters lowers anxiety and depressive symptoms and increases life satisfaction (Catalino & Fredrickson, 2011). Overall, joy creates long term psychological resources that protect and enhance mental health in addition to contributing to instant experiences of happiness.

Here, joy is mainly described in terms of the broaden and build hypothesis, which states that some positive emotions, like joy, spread one's perspective and behavior to improve the discovery of new thoughts and behavior patterns (Fredrickson & Levenson, 1998). Joy reinforces adaptive behaviors that promote mental health by activating brain regions linked to reward processing and motivation, including the prefrontal cortex and the ventral striatum (Kringelbach & Berridge, 2017). These brain reactions not only produce pleasurable feelings right away, but they also reinforce adaptive behaviors like problem-solving and social connection, which are critical for long-term mental health. Dopaminergic pathways, specifically those that connect the striatum and prefrontal cortex are essential for maintaining happiness and fostering resistance against mood disorders (Heller et al., 2009). Greater quantities of joy may be connected to reduced levels of anxiety and depression because neuroimaging studies indicate that these people have more connectivity in brain networks linked to emotional regulation (Waugh et al., 2015).

Gratitude

Gratitude, which is frequently thought of as a pleasant emotional reaction to advantages received from others, is essential for improving psychological health and developing connections with others (Emmons & McCullough, 2003). Gratitude, like other good emotions, has been demonstrated to facilitate the development of social and psychological resources and to broaden one's behaviour and mental processes (Fredrickson, 2004). Gratitude has been linked to higher levels of everyday positive emotions and decreased levels of negative ones, as well as better overall well-being (McCullough et al., 2002; Kashdan et al., 2006). Gratitude has several beneficial emotional and social effects, including reduced stress (Wood et al., 2008), fewer depressive symptoms (Lambert et al., 2012), and enhanced feelings of relationships and the perception of social support (Wood et al., 2008). Since acts of gratitude are frequently linked to improved psychological well-being, there is a close connection between gratitude and mental health. Regular gratitude practitioners express greater optimism and life satisfaction as well as decreased levels of anxiety and sadness (Wood et al., 2010). Thus, gratitude supports the good aspects of mental health and safeguards against mental illnesses like anxiety and depression. This is consistent with the larger idea that well-being includes both the presence of happiness and the absence of pain.

Gratitude has been shown to improve students' subjective well-being in India. Higher capacity for gratitude levels was positively connected with happiness and life satisfaction among Indian college students (Kumar & Dixit, 2017). This suggests that the capacity

for gratitude has a role in promoting well-being in collectivist cultural contexts. Similar results have been seen in eastern samples, where greater mental health and stability in social connections are highly predicted by gratitude (Loo et al., 2014). These results suggest that gratitude serves as a relational resource for well-being as well as an individual strength. Gratitude is not only a feeling; it is also a mental quality, a coping mechanism, and even a moral quality (Emmons & Crumpler, 2000).

Being aware of and grateful for wonderful things that happen and taking the time to show gratitude is what Niemiec (2018) characterized as gratitude, a known character strength. According to Park et al. (2004), it is also linked to traits like kindness, love, hope, spirituality, zest, meaningful life, and job satisfaction. Macfarlane (2019) investigated character strengths and confirmed that they are a person's ability to think, feel, and act. According to Peterson and Seligman (2004), when these are all in equilibrium, people can thrive in life. Niemiec (2014) asserted that these are the activities that we enjoy and that naturally occur to us since our brains are programmed to conduct them as a result of repeated experience. In this outstanding work, Seligman (2011) outlined his PERMA model, which consists of the following elements: positive emotions, engagement, positive relationships, meaning, and accomplishment, as the foundation of a flourishing existence and the path to well-being.

Numerous advantages of gratitude have been demonstrated for both the general public and nurses in particular, with the former showing better physical and psychological evidence and symptoms such as reduced BP, better sleep, increased care, and self-care (Randolph, 2017). Gaining this ability could assist reduce work-related stress and provide better interactions with the clinical staff and patients. It can also enhance decision-making, boost productivity, and develop management abilities (Amin, 2013). According to Starkey et al. (2019), improved physical health in terms of eating, sleeping, and satisfaction was positively correlated with more instances of receiving gratitude at work.

Optimism and Hope

At its most fundamental level, optimism is inversely correlated with hopelessness, which is a depressive risk factor (Alloy et al., 2006). Positive mental health outcomes have been consistently associated optimistic tend to have better levels of life satisfaction, increased ability to handle stress, and reduced anxiety and depression. Around the world, academics have debated the impact of hope and optimism on both mental and physical health (Milona, 2020). Both points of view produce positive outcomes, based upon empirical evidence (Schiavon et al., 2017; Pleeing et al., 2021). Optimism is a cognitive variable that conveys a person's positive angle on the future (Carver & Scheier, 2019). Optimists tend to have more hopeful goals than pessimistic ones and face less difficulty in their daily lives, even when they face difficulties (Carver et al., 2010). The events that are expected to happen in the future could have an impact on people's daily lives, health, and techniques for managing stress and emotions. Optimists are more focused on high objectives than the methods or reasons for reaching them (Carver & Scheier, 2002). Research has shown that optimism is linked to better well-being, reduced attrition rates, less depressive symptoms, and more favorable social support perceptions (Forgeard & Seligman, 2012; Schug et al., 2021).

Hope is a three-component condition of positive motivation:

objectives (goals), pathways (planning), and agency (Snyder, 1991; Schiavon et al., 2017). Hope theory places a strong focus on the existence of individual agency in relation to objectives and the identification of methods for achieving them (Snyder, 2002). According to Gallagher and Lopez (2009), a hopeful individual would therefore support statements like "I will achieve my goal," "I have a plan [...] to achieve this goal," and "I am motivated and confident in my ability to use this plan to achieve this goal." Recent studies have shown that a person's degree of hope is frequently influenced by their intrinsic character traits as well as psychosocial factors (such as social support, goal-concordant care, & success in achieving goals & dealing with stressors), physiological factors, and environmental factors (Corn et al., 2020). As a driving force for progress, hope supports mental wellness in general and can be beneficial in the recovery of particular illnesses, such as severe mental disease, thoughts about committing suicide, anxiety, depression and trauma-related problems (Hunag et al., 2015; Gallagher et al., 2020; Tomasulo, 2020; Sari et al., 2021). Additionally, Research show that hope has a greater positive impact on well-being than optimism (Krafft et al., 2021) as well studies reveal that hope is strongly related to several psychosocial procedures and results, such as social support, a greater feeling of life's purpose, higher perceptions of life's meaning, positive affect, emotional adjustment, coping with illness and improved life satisfaction (Corn et al., 2020; Long et al., 2020).

Love

Love is a powerful and complicated feeling that includes intense care, attachment, worry, and affection for another individual (Fehr & Sprecher, 2009). It is frequently defined as a combination of behavioral, cognitive, and emotional elements, encompassing sentiments of intimacy, warmth, compassion, dedication, and selflessness (Hazan & Shaver, 1987). Love provides a feeling of being connected, emotional stability, and societal support which all are beneficial for mental health (Brown & Brown, 2006). According to research, loving and close relationships improve life satisfaction and lower the risk of anxiety and depression (Reis & Gable, 2015). Love has an impact on one's health and well-being. Our appreciation of the importance and strength of love's influence on mental and physical health increases with our understanding of the specific neurobiology of love and its potential secondary implications (Komisaruk & Whipple, 1998). Love has become a part of comprehensive psychological study as well as basic science studies, such as neurobiology, and clinical medicine because of its close connection to the concepts of pleasure and positive psychology, or happy mental states (Esch et al., 2004; Esch & Stefano, 2005). By controlling cortisol and increasing oxytocin release, which fosters serenity and bonding, loving relationships reduce stress (Heinrichs et al., 2009). Because love offers emotional security and social support, research indicates that those with close, loving relationships are less likely to experience anxiety and depression (Fehr & Sprecher, 2009).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this review highlights the role of positive emotions such as joy, gratitude, optimism, and hope in mental health. It has been demonstrated that the positive emotion approach helps to improve mental health. Research shows that increasing positive emotion can reduce the symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress

meanwhile promoting life satisfaction, well-being and happiness. Positive emotion is shown to improve coping mechanisms and build relationships with others, which support psychological growth and long-term resilience. They encourage increased creativity and cognitive flexibility, which empower people to develop coping strategies and create to produce innovative answers to life's problems. Long-term mental health is protected by positive emotions, which also promote emotional stability and act as a buffer against the beginnings of psychological diseases.

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